

Tunable Photonic Analog-to-Digital Conversion enabled by a Dispersion-Diversity Multicore Fiber

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Abstract: We propose and demonstrate, for the first time, tunable photonic-assisted time-interleaved analog-to-digital conversion based on a customized dispersion-diversity multicore fiber, providing sampling rates from 25 up to 125 GS/s.

1. Introduction

The exploitation of photonic technologies to enable analog-to-digital conversion (ADC) becomes essential to overcome the bottleneck of their electronic counterparts, mainly in terms of bandwidth and timing jitter, [1,2]. In particular, photonic-assisted ADCs, where electronics benefit from the inherent advantages of photonics to enhance some of its limiting properties while the quantization is made by electronic ADCs, [1], are interesting due to their direct compatibility with current optical communications networks bringing, as a consequence, a cost-effective solution. By using N parallel electronic ADCs to process, at the same time, N different replicas of the incoming signal, photonic-assisted ADCs can increase the effective sampling rate beyond the limits of electronic ADCs while allowing real-time operation. Over the past few decades, a rich variety of photonic-assisted techniques for wideband ADCs have been developed, including optically clocked time-interleaving configurations, [3], or photonic time-stretching schemes, [4]. Here, we propose and experimentally demonstrate, for the first time, photonic time-interleaved ADC based on a customized dispersion-diversity heterogeneous multicore fiber (MCF).

2. Results

Fig. 1 depicts the operation principle of the proposed ADC architecture, where a single heterogeneous MCF, which is custom designed to operate as a tunable sampled true-time delay line (TTDL), provides a set of parallel delayed replicas of the input signal. It consists of 7 distinct dispersion-engineered trench-assisted cores whose chromatic dispersions are tailored “à la carte” to provide a constant differential group delay between cores tunable with the optical wavelength, [5]. The fabricated fiber is 5-km long and satisfies tunable TTDL operation for cores 3-7, whose measured chromatic dispersions are 16.3 to 20.3 ps/km/nm with incremental steps of 1 ps/km/nm.

Fig. 1. Operation principle and experimental setup for the photonic-assisted time-interleaved ADC based on a dispersion-diversity heterogeneous MCF. PC: Polarization controller; RF: Radiofrequency; EDFA: Erbium doped fiber amplifier; PD: photodetector.

As Fig. 1 shows, a periodic triangular waveform with a period of 800 ps generated by an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) modulates the optical signal by means of an electro-optic modulator (EOM) and is injected into

cores 3-7 of the MCF. At the fiber output, a set of variable optical attenuators (VOAs) equalize the signal amplitudes. The signals are then photodetected and amplified independently and visualized in a digital phosphor oscilloscope (DPO). The measured waveforms at each core are digitally sampled and time-interleaved to obtain the equivalent sampling rate of the resulting photonic-assisted ADC, $f_{s,eq}$. Fig. 2 illustrates the implemented ADC process for 2 different optical wavelengths. Fig. 2(a-c) represent, respectively, the measured waveforms, the temporal digital sampling, and the time-interleaving at the optical wavelength $\lambda = 1538$ nm. Fig. 2(d-e) show, respectively, the measured waveforms, the temporal digital sampling, and the time-interleaving at the optical wavelength $\lambda = 1531.6$ nm. We see how the differential delay between replicas increases as the optical wavelength increases. In particular, the differential time delay between adjacent replicas is $\Delta\tau = 8$ and 40 ps, respectively for $\lambda = 1531.6$ and 1538 nm, as expected from the measured group delay slopes of Fig. 1. The required sampling rates for the parallel electronic ADCs are then 25 and 5 GS/s, respectively for $\lambda = 1531.6$ and 1538 nm, so that after digital interleaving $f_{s,eq}$ increases up to 125 and 25 GS/s, respectively. All in all, the proposed photonic-assisted time-interleaved ADC offers a sampling rate N times higher than that of the commercial electronic ADCs used, being N the number of samples of the TTDL. In our experiment, $N = 5$, so that we require 5 electronic ADCs with lower sampling rate to achieve a high-speed ADC by performing the optical replication and time-interleaving processes.

Fig. 2. (a) Measured waveforms, (b) sampling and (c) time-interleaving for cores 3-7 at the optical wavelength $\lambda = 1538$ nm. (d) Measured waveforms, (e) sampling and (f) time-interleaving at $\lambda = 1531.6$ nm. Different colors relate to the different core signals.

3. Conclusions and discussion

We have proposed and experimentally demonstrated, for the first time to our knowledge, a new approach for photonic-assisted time-interleaved analog-to-digital conversion based on a dispersion-diversity heterogeneous MCF. The MCF is 5-km long and comprises 7 different trench-assisted cores whose refractive index profiles were properly designed to behave as a tunable sampled TTDL. We successfully demonstrated continuous sampling rate tunability from 25 up to 125 GS/s by sweeping the optical wavelength of operation from 1538 down to 1531.6 nm.

The use of a MCF to provide parallel channel transmission brings the advantage of increased compactness and environmental stability, providing more control of possible random channel misalignments than other fiber parallel configurations. In particular, the measured TTDL temporal stability is within a 150-fs maximum variability range (2-hour time measurements in laboratory conditions with maximum temperature variation below 1° C), which is in the order of the current best-case jitter performance of commercial electronic ADCs. All in all, our approach provides unique performance benefits in terms of ADC sampling rate multiplication factor, continuous sampling rate tunability and remote system reconfigurability.

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